

Research Paper

Modelling the market diffusion of hydrogen-based steel and basic chemical production in Europe – A site-specific approach

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ABSTRACT

Climate-neutral hydrogen is a promising option to replace fossil fuels and reduce greenhouse gas emissions in energy-intensive industries. At the same time, spatial and timely dynamics of hydrogen market diffusion are uncertain. This study simulates the market diffusion of hydrogen-based production routes for the entire European plant stock of primary steel, high-value chemicals, methanol, and ammonia production sites. The model includes a total of 158 plants at 96 sites and explicitly considers hydrogen infrastructure, plant ages, production capacities and reinvestment cycles. Sixteen scenario sensitivities were defined to analyse various future hydrogen and carbon dioxide price pathways. The results show that one investment opportunity remains until 2050 for all plants, while 36% of plants require reinvestment before 2030. The cost-competitiveness of hydrogen-based production varies across products: Methanol and high-value chemicals can only be competitive with hydrogen prices below 60 €/MWh. For steel, a high carbon dioxide price and natural gas-fired direct reduction can mitigate fossil lock-ins using natural gas as bridging option towards full use of hydrogen. The study highlights the risk of reinvesting in fossil technologies without additional policies. The maximum technical hydrogen demand potential is 1000 TWh, but considering techno-economic limitations in the sensitivities, only 64 to 507 TWh can be reached. The planned future hydrogen network matches most reinvestment needs.

1. Introduction

CO₂ mitigation is essential if the European Union (EU) is to achieve its target of being climate-neutral by 2050 and industry currently accounts for 21% of European CO₂ emissions [1]. The EU's ambitious climate targets, embedded in initiatives like the European Green Deal, Fit-for-55 [2] and REPowerEU [3], demand a profound restructuring of its industrial landscape. Central to this transformation is the integration of renewable energy sources and innovative climate-neutral processes. However, one major challenge is the development of a pan-European infrastructure to enable the use of hydrogen, particularly in heavy industries such as steel, high-value chemicals (HVC; containing olefins and

aromatics), ammonia, and methanol production. These industries are expected to be major consumers of hydrogen (H₂) in the future [4].

This transformation is not only needed to meet climate targets but is also essential to safeguard the competitiveness of European industries at global level. Energy system modelling tools can be used to support policymakers, researchers, and industry experts in exploring different scenarios and identifying the optimal pathways for this transformation. Assessing the impact of different strategies to guide policy formulation and investment decisions requires a profound understanding of the intricate interplay between industrial strategies and energy system dynamics. Here, the existing modelling tools are limited in terms of the detailed representation of industrial sectors and their transition

Abbreviations: ABM, Agent-based modelling; ASU, Air separation unit; BF, Blast furnace; BOF, Basic oxygen furnace; CAPEX, Capital expenditure; CCfD, Carbon contract for difference; CCS, Carbon capture and storage; CCU, Carbon capture and utilisation; CCU/S, Carbon capture and utilisation or storage; CO₂, Carbon dioxide; DRI, Direct reduced iron; EAF, Electric arc furnace; EHB, European hydrogen backbone; EU, European Union; EU ETS, European Union Emission Trading System; E-PRTR, European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register; GHG, Greenhouse gas; H₂, Hydrogen; H₂-DRI, Direct reduced iron using hydrogen; HVC, High Value Chemicals; IPCEI, Important projects of common European interest; ISI, Institute for Systems- and Innovation Research; MtA, Methanol-to-aromatics; MtO, Methanol-to-olefins; MtHVC, Methanol-to-high value chemicals; NG, Natural gas; NG-DRI, Direct reduced iron using natural gas; OPEX, Operational expenditure; SAF, Sustainable aviation fuel; SEC, Specific energy consumption; SMR, Steam methane reforming; TRL, Technology readiness level.

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dynamics. Enhancing both the granularity and spatial detail in modelling and data is crucial to better support strategic energy planning.

1.1. Challenges in industry modelling

Each industrial site has unique properties in terms of its history and geography, which have been neglected in recent energy modelling approaches. Industry differs from other demand sectors due to long lifetimes and huge individual investments [5]. However, existing models mostly describe technology diffusion based on statistical changes over time at an aggregated level. Examples are technology stock approaches, in which statistical distribution lead to gradual replacements over time when installations reach the end of their useful lives [6]. Other approaches set exogenous diffusion rates [7]. Varying the parameters and techno-economic assumptions leads to the exploration of different transition pathways, but without taking into account the individual industrial plants or spatial resolution [8]. Even the existing agent-based approaches assume exogenous decommissioning profiles and neglect spatial properties [9]. Only a few approaches in the literature have tried to model the diffusion of new technologies by considering the age structure of the respective plant fleets [10]. Established energy system optimisation models, which represent industrial sectors in an aggregated manner, often provide only sectoral resolution and fail to include site or process details [11]. Industry demands in energy system models are mostly specified on country level [12]. As a result, the existing models are limited about industrial transition at the level of individual plants and sites. In the context of industrial transformation, however, it is crucial to develop a comprehensive understanding of the intricate relationship between spatial and temporal dynamics within the energy system.

A site-specific analysis provides a granular perspective to determine plant-specific energy demand and the energy infrastructure this requires. High spatial resolution is required to better understand the role of infrastructure like hydrogen, gas and electricity networks [13]. Recently, the very first attempts have been made to use site-specific open-source industry data to assess the implications for energy infrastructures [14]. In addition, industry modelling needs to be improved with regard to specific discrete investments and their regional allocation. Modelling discrete reinvestments makes it possible to consider windows of opportunity for investing in climate-neutral processes and the risks of potential fossil fuel lock-ins [5].

1.2. The role of hydrogen in the energy transition

Analysing the potential future role of hydrogen infrastructure in a CO₂-neutral energy system requires industry models with high spatial resolution and a realistic representation of reinvestment cycles. As stated by many recent studies, hydrogen could significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions and contribute to achieving the EU's ambitious climate goals [15]. The use of hydrogen or its derivatives is prominently discussed in various applications throughout the energy system [16]. Also hydrogen trade flows within Europe and the role of hydrogen storage are relevant in recent research [17]. The EU has taken significant steps towards embracing hydrogen as a key enabler of industrial transformation, driven by the imperatives of decarbonisation, energy security, and economic competitiveness. Hydrogen, especially when produced using renewable energy sources through processes like electrolysis, offers a clean alternative to fossil fuels, and is a viable solution for decarbonising various industrial sectors [18]. Introducing hydrogen as an energy carrier as part of the domestic energy supply requires additional infrastructures and process adjustments in energy-consuming plants [19]. Increasing activities can be observed in political initiatives like REPowerEU [3], numerous publicly and privately funded projects like the Important Projects of Common European Interest (IPCEI) hydrogen programme and initiatives like the European Hydrogen Backbone (EHB) [20]. Many initiatives draw on the existing

literature on hydrogen with regard to future demand [18], supply optimisation [21], imports [22], infrastructure needs [23], and global trade [24]. However, these studies are often based on analyses at national or international level and often present hydrogen infrastructures as schematic flows based on a fixed number of nodes [23]. Thus, hydrogen modelling in the demand sectors is often only partly regionalised, e.g. by using distribution keys in a top-down approach [25]. In contrast, detailed regional results exist for the optimisation of renewable power plants and power grids [26].

1.3. Research question and scope

The current literature on energy system analysis indicates a research gap concerning high resolution hydrogen demand from industry at an individual plant site level. Therefore, a novel modelling approach is applied to improve the accuracy of industry representation, which covers the entire fleet of European heavy-industry sites and plants with high spatial resolution. The proposed simulation model provides a flexible method to represent the investment decision-making behaviour of individual industries. The age structure of the current plant stock allows for the recognition of reinvestment cycles in industry, capture limitations of technology diffusion, and provides the necessary level of detail that can be used for further infrastructure modelling and planning. This paper investigates the diffusion patterns of hydrogen-based processes for the industrial production of primary steel, HVC, ammonia and methanol and aims to answer the following research question:

What are the potential diffusion pathways for hydrogen in the production of primary steel and basic chemicals considering restrictions due to the age structure of the current plant stock, policy instruments and infrastructure availability? How do diffusion dynamics compare across different industrial sectors?

The method is based on modelling individual investment decisions as a discrete choice among alternative technologies with total cost of ownership as the main decision criterion. The investigation includes 16 sensitivities for a broad range of hydrogen and CO₂ price trajectories and focus on four selected energy-intensive products. These are steel, HVC, methanol and ammonia, which are all expected to require high quantities of hydrogen for climate-neutral production and a connection to hydrogen transport infrastructure. The focus on the regional scope is EU27 + 3 (Norway, Switzerland and UK) and consider a total of 158 production units at 96 industrial sites. The method can, however, also be applied to other world regions, products and industry sectors. The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the method and main assumptions, and section 3 the results. The analysis of results compares the individual products and the 16 sensitivities in their spatial and temporal dynamics and investigates the underlying driving forces including the role of re-investment cycles and economic competitiveness. Structural differences between the products are shown and risks of fossil lock-ins are identified. After analysing technology diffusion patterns and their spatial distribution, the potential regional limitations of hydrogen availability based on the planned European hydrogen backbone is assessed. Based on this, conclusions in terms of investment needs, hydrogen demand and greenhouse gas emissions are summarised. A comprehensive data annex provides a full list of input data and assumptions plus extended data results with high spatial and temporal resolution. These can be used for further energy system analysis.

2. Method and data

This section briefly introduces the method steps for modelling as well as the required data input and its collection as well as relevant assumptions made for this analysis.

2.1. Method

The newly developed model is written in Python and described in detail by Neuwirth et al. [27]. Here, only the core elements required to understand the results in the context of this work are presented. The model considers the specific characteristics of individual industrial sites to simulate investment decisions in new (low-carbon) production processes. Costs are assumptions and depend on the scenario settings, such as energy carrier price projections, policy instruments and local infrastructures. A short description is given in Appendix A. By integrating the choice algorithm into an industry stock approach that tracks individual plant ages and reinvestment cycles are considered the main restrictions on transition dynamics.

To investigate the transition towards hydrogen-based primary steel and basic chemical production in Europe up to 2050, the model uses site-specific information for each plant from the Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase. This represents energy-intensive industries in detail by merging data from several sources [28]. The focus is on primary steel and the basic chemicals HVC, ammonia and methanol as these industry applications have the highest potential and best technology readiness for using green hydrogen [18]. Figure 1 provides an overview of the methodology used for data gathering and validation as well as of its application and results:

- 1. Data gathering and validation:** The database is updated to incorporate the most recent available information for primary steel and basic chemicals sites and validated manually by screening literature, company websites, and press releases as well as information provided by industrial associations and other research projects (section 2.2.1). Conventional and alternative processes are retrieved from previous modelling activities and further literature, see section 2.2.2).
- 2. Application of the technology diffusion model:** The validated dataset is used as model input and the theoretical reinvestment cycles of the existing plant stock is analysed. Based on a defined

scenario as well as process-specific techno-economic data and dependence on the EHB, the model calculates transformation pathways for 16 combinations of hydrogen and CO₂ prices (4 variations each).

- 3. Result analysis:** The results show possible diffusion pathways for hydrogen in primary steel and basic chemicals production. The georeferenced modelling of individual plants with high spatial resolution makes it possible to consider the interplay with the planned hydrogen infrastructure according to the EHB. Parameters like projections of energy demand, investments and emission reduction are analysed.

2.2. Data

The data used as input to the model in this analysis are taken from a database of industrial production sites for the above-mentioned basic chemicals and primary steel merged with site information and process-specific techno-economic parameters. All the data used for this analysis are prepared as supplementary material.

2.2.1. Developing a dataset for the entire fleet of steel and chemical sites in Europe

The Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase contains information for each plant and site. It is based on matching the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR) [29] and European Union Emission Trading System (EU ETS) [30] databases. The spatial scope of the analysis is EU27+3. Additional information for the primary steel production sites was taken from the VDEh steel Plantfacts database [31] for the base year 2015. These data were updated and validated using additional information from Eurofer [32] and Global Steel Plant Tracker [33]. Appendix B 1 shows the detailed number of plants per product and process for each country. 58 blast furnaces (BF), most in combination with basic oxygen furnaces (BOF), are currently in operation at 28 sites across all countries with one plant using direct reduced iron (DRI) fired with natural gas (NG-DRI) in combination with an electric arc furnace

Fig. 1. Methodology for data gathering, model application and results analysis for primary steel and basic chemicals in EU27+3 within this study

(EAF) for primary steel production. Currently, no primary steel plant using hydrogen-based direct reduction (H₂-DRI) is in operation. Unlike the iron and steel sector, no known databases exist for the chemical sector. Thus, data collection on parameters like production capacity and age was based on numerous sources per product. For HVC production, cracker capacities are given by Petrochemicals Europe [34]. Further information, e.g. plant age, was gathered from the history sections of individual company websites and press releases (Appendix B 2). Across Europe, 47 steam crackers operate at 37 different sites. A similar approach was taken for ammonia, where data on capacities and ages were derived from reports [35]. Those were updated and cross-checked with recent publications [36], press releases, and company websites were consulted for manual validation and to incorporate the most recent available information (Appendix B 3). In total, 45 ammonia plants currently produce at 34 sites. In addition, 7 methanol plants operate at 6 sites, for which information was gathered manually (Appendix B 4). For both ammonia and methanol, it is assumed that the required synthesis gas is produced via steam reforming (SMR). However, plants for the different chemical products are partly located at the same sites, which leads to a total of 68 sites for the chemical products covered.

In order to be able to carry out a comprehensive and holistic transformation analysis of the selected industrial sectors at a national and a European level, it is first necessary to ensure the completeness of the data with regard to industrial sites and plants. Validation of the completeness based on production capacities is addressed in Appendix C and Appendix D.

2.2.2. Techno-economic input at process level

To feed the model with process-specific data in order to run the algorithm on investment decision, literature and process research is conducted to collect data with the necessary granularity.

Here, specification on the chemical compound has to be made. In this study, a typical composition of naphtha-based steam crackers is assumed to be replaced by a combination of methanol-to-olefins (MtO) and methanol-to-aromatics (MtA) process. The average composition is derived from the Prodcom [37] database on European level, showing the following shares for 2019: 41% ethylene, 31% propylene, 5% butene, 15% benzene, 3% toluene, and 5% xylenes. The techno-economic assumptions, such as capital expenditure (CAPEX) or specific energy consumption (SEC), are built by reflecting on these product shares. Following, methanol-to-HVC (MtHVC) describes the combination of

both MtO and MtA. Consolidated techno-economic data at process level are listed in Table 1.

As mentioned above, in this analysis, plant age and reinvestment cycles are considered the main drivers of process diffusion in industry. These are evaluated in more detailed in Appendix E. To meet the identified process-specific demands, different energy carriers have specific shares in the individual processes as estimated in Table 2. For the DRI options on primary steel production, shares of natural gas and hydrogen are also partially necessary as reductants.

Based on the assumptions on averaged energy and fuel demand as well as energy carrier shares, the resulting energy and steam demand per plant and site can be used to calculate emissions by applying the emission factor per energy carrier from Table 3.

Electricity and hydrogen do not show emission factors, as their use does not lead to direct CO₂ emissions according to the definition of scope 1 emissions in the EU ETS [30]. Moreover, electricity and hydrogen within this analysis were assumed to be climate-neutral in order to reach the targeted climate neutrality in 2050. The described assumptions and detailed process data make it possible to use the model to conduct simulations of competing processes using the individual industrial sites.

2.2.3. Scenario assumptions

Scenarios are defined by setting parameters that are not related to the previously described input data at site and process level. In the presented analysis, national production is assumed to be constant over time. The developed scenario includes a set of prices for fossil fuels and electricity. Hydrogen and CO₂ price paths are expected to have a strong impact on the results of the possible technology diffusion paths for hydrogen-based processes and are also associated with high uncertainty. In total, 16 sensitivities of varying hydrogen and CO₂ prices are applied (4 variations each). These assumptions are briefly described in the following and summarized in Table 4. The scenario represents a realistic “best guess” in terms of fossil fuel and electricity prices. All energy carrier prices have been affected by recent developments. Consequently, the medium to high prices for electricity and fossils decrease strongly until 2030 and then remain on a higher level than pre-crisis from Covid pandemic and the Russian invasion. Hydrogen infrastructure based on EHB plans is considered to provide hydrogen to individual industry sites without capacity restrictions and with maximum availability. The underlying assumption is that an industry site can access hydrogen from the EHB if the distance between pipeline and site is less than 30 km. The

Table 1
Techno-economic model input per process.¹

Product	Process	CAPEX ² (€/tCap)	OPEX ³ (€/t)	Lifetime (yr)	Fuel demand (GJ/t)	Steam demand (GJ/t)	Feedstock demand (GJ/t)	Electricity demand (GJ/t)
Steel, primary	BF/BOF	170 [38]	295 [39]	20 [40,41]	16.7 [42]	0.92	0	1.1
	NG-DRI/EAF	795 [38]	340 [39]	25 [43]	9 [4339,44]	0	0	2.1 [4546]
	H ₂ -DRI/EAF	795 [38]	340 [39]	25 [43]	6.8 [45]	0	0	1.7 [45]
HVC ⁴	Steam cracker	1700 [47]	60	25 [48]	33.9 [47,49]	0	102.5 [47,49]	1.4
	Methanol-to-HVC	1000 [47]	25	30	0	0.8	138.9 [47,50]	0
Ammonia	Ammonia SMR	550 [51,52]	30	25 [53]	9.4 [54]	-1.8	21.36 [42]	3.2 [55]
	Ammonia H ₂	110	40	25 [53]	0	-0.9	21.36 [42]	4.8 [47]
Methanol ⁵	Methanol SMR	590 [51,56,57]	21 [56]	25 [58]	12.1 [42]	-0.9	22.6 [42]	0.5
	Methanol H ₂	300 [59]	50	25 [58]	0	0.4	22.6 [42]	0.8 [56]

Primary steel: DRI/EAF greenfield; BF/BOF brownfield.

HVC: MtHVC greenfield; Steam cracker brownfield.

Ammonia: SMR brownfield + HB adjustments; Green hydrogen (grid) air separation unit (ASU) greenfield + HB adjustments.

Methanol: SMR brownfield + methanol synthesis adjustments + purification brownfield adjustments; Green hydrogen (grid) methanol synthesis and purification brownfield adjustments.

¹ Values were derived from thorough literature research and merged with information from experts and own calculations based on the internal FORECAST database.

² The values for CAPEX consider greenfield or brownfield investments, depending on the process.

³ Apart from labour and maintenance costs, operational costs (OPEX) also include material costs that are not represented by energy carriers (e.g. iron ore, scrap and alloying elements for primary steel).

⁴ Values on energy and feedstock demand were calibrated to ton of ethylene production for calculations but include the demand for complete HVC production. All energetic values refer to the LHV.

⁵ Carbon for methanol production is assumed to be provided at zero cost not specifying the source.

Table 2
Used energy carriers and respective energy carrier shares for fuel and steam and feedstock demand per process.

Product	Process	Coal	Natural gas	Derived gases	Hydrogen	Naphtha
Fuel and steam shares						
Steel, primary	Blast furnace	0.76	0.07	0.17	0	0
	NG-DRI	0	1	0	0	0
	H2-DRI	0	0	0	1	0
HVC	Steam cracking	0	1	0	0	0
Ammonia	Ammonia SMR	0	1	0	0	0
Methanol	Methanol SMR	0	1	0	0	0
Feedstock shares						
HVC	Steam cracking	0	0	0	0	1
	Methanol-to-HVC	0	0	0	1	0
Ammonia	Ammonia SMR	0	1	0	0	0
	Ammonia H2	0	0	0	1	0
Methanol	Methanol SMR	0	1	0	0	0
	Methanol H2	0	0	0	1	0

Table 3
Emission factors per energy carrier in tCO₂/GJ.

Energy carrier	tCO ₂ /GJ
Electricity	0
Coal	0.096
Natural gas	0.056
Derived gases	0
Naphtha	0.076
Hydrogen	0

EHB is assumed to provide sufficient long- and short-term storage capacity (e.g., via underground cavern storage), and the hydrogen prices include this. In the long term, this is regarded as the cost-optimal solution compared to decentralized storage solutions. In the short term and

during the construction of the hydrogen grid, decentralized generation and storage solutions at the industrial site might play a certain role, which is not considered in this analysis.

The qualitatively described key assumptions from Table 4 are visualised as a time series for detailed comparison. As an in-depth analysis of all countries within this publication is too extensive, the focus is set on Germany in parts of the results section. Germany is the country with the highest number of sites and plants for the considered products.

Therefore, the price assumptions for Germany are highlighted within the shaded price range for all countries for electricity, natural gas, naphtha and coal (Figure 2) as well as CO₂ and hydrogen (Figure 3). All sensitivities for hydrogen prices assume a decreasing trend until 2050. There are variations for the CO₂ price, which increases from roughly 80

Table 4
Scenario definitions and corresponding key assumptions

Indicator	Unit	Quantitative example: Germany			
		2022	2030	2040	2050
Description	Medium short-term price shocks due to Covid pandemic and Russian invasion of Ukraine without huge long-term effects. This scenario reflects a realistic or best guess estimation concerning conventional energy prices				
Electricity price	€/GJ	62.7	41	37.6	34.2
Natural gas price	€/GJ _{LHV}	18	8.7	7.8	7
Naphtha price	€/GJ _{LHV}	22.6	13	12.7	12.4
Coal price	€/GJ _{LHV}	4.5	3.4	3.2	2.9
Fuel oil price	€/GJ _{LHV}	22.6	13	12.7	12.4
Energy availability	GJ _{LHV}	unrestricted	unrestricted	unrestricted	unrestricted
Production	ton	2019 calibration	2019 calibration	2019 calibration	2019 calibration
Sensitivities	Sensitivities are conducted with same assumptions on electricity and fossil energy prices. They differ in hydrogen and CO ₂ price assumptions (4 variations each) and thus result in 16 sensitivity combinations.				
Variation		v1 / v2 / v3 / v4	v1 / v2 / v3 / v4	v1 / v2 / v3 / v4	v1 / v2 / v3 / v4
Hydrogen price	€/GJ _{LHV}	27 / 37 / 45 / 57	20 / 27 / 33 / 40	17.5 / 23.5 / 29 / 35	15 / 20 / 25 / 30
CO ₂ price	€/GJ	80 / 80 / 80 / 80	129 / 143 / 157 / 171	189 / 221 / 254 / 286	250 / 300 / 350 / 400

Fig. 2. Electricity and fossil price ranges for all countries considered. The price series for Germany is highlighted as an example of trajectory of one country.

Fig. 3. Sensitivities on hydrogen and CO₂ prices for all countries

€/tCO₂ at present to different higher prices by 2050 (250 €/tCO₂, 300 €/tCO₂, 350 €/tCO₂, 400 €/tCO₂).

The variations shown in Figure 3 for the hydrogen price seem to be very optimistic, especially the lower price paths. However, recent studies indicate that hydrogen prices could fall to between 15 and 20 €/GJ, which is the range of the two lower hydrogen price paths for 2050 in this analysis [60].

Other studies show wider ranges, but also the prospect of future hydrogen production costs in Europe below the assumptions made here [61]. Even lower hydrogen production costs are published in latest literature including salt cavern storage [62], but additional costs for transport and without stating the amount of hydrogen that can be produced to those low-cost conditions.

3. Results

This section presents and analyses the results of the scenarios defined in section 2.2.3 on an aggregated European level. However, as the model calculates all the results bottom-up at plant level for each individual site and plant, more detailed results per country are provided in table and bar chart format in supplementary excel files.

3.1. Market diffusion drivers

Reinvestment cycles based on the plant ages of the existing plant stock and economic competitiveness are analysed concerning their

impact on the market diffusion.

3.1.1. Reinvestment cycles

The model only allows new investments in hydrogen-based processes if the existing process reaches its assumed end of life. Consequently, the theoretically cumulated phase-out of the current plant stock determines the maximum diffusion speed for new investments (not considering early replacement or retrofitting). Figure 4 shows the theoretical reinvestments for all plants in EU27+3 for the considered products. It becomes clear that, in theory, complete replacement of the entire plant fleet is still possible by 2050 by following theoretical reinvestment cycles. However, at the same time, it is clear for most plants that there is not more than one reinvestment cycle remaining until 2050.

Across all plants, about 39% of production capacity requires replacement until 2030 and about 68% by 2035. This early need for reinvestments constitutes a high risk of lock-ins in fossil fuel-based processes, because hydrogen-based processes are not yet economically competitive (section 3.1.2). In addition, hydrogen may not be available in sufficient quantities.

Comparing the individual products reveals a diverse picture (Figure 4). Around 42% of blast furnaces, 41% of steam crackers (HVC production), and 51% of methanol plants require reinvestments by 2030. In contrast, only 22% of European ammonia plants need reinvestments by 2030.

Theoretically, a lifetime of 20 years as assumed for blast furnaces would allow for a second cycle of reinvestment before 2050 for some

Fig. 4. Theoretical phase-out of current conventional plant stock in EU27+3 according to plant age and typical lifetimes for primary steel, HVC, ammonia and methanol plants

plants. For the other products, lifetimes are expected to be 25 years (Appendix E), which reduces the potential for a second reinvestment cycle. Thus, the potential to replace early reinvestments in fossil-based processes before 2050 is very limited.

To better understand the risk of lock-ins, the following sections assess the economic competitiveness and the availability of hydrogen infrastructure over the entire period.

3.1.2. Economic competitiveness

The economic competitiveness of hydrogen-based processes varies across the countries depending on their national energy prices. This variation is an important factor that explains the differing speed of technology diffusion in Europe. This assessment focuses on Germany, which has the highest manufacturing capacity for the investigated products with 39 plants at 25 sites (Appendix B 1). CO₂ avoidance costs are investigated as the main indicator for the economic competitiveness.

Figure 5 compares the CO₂ avoidance costs for the three steelmaking processes. The break-even points for switching from BF to NG-DRI are around 120 to 130 €/tCO₂, which is before 2030 for all the assumed CO₂ price trajectories. The break-even point for switching from BF to H2-DRI ranges from 100 to 180 €/tCO₂ and is highly dependent on the hydrogen price. For both options, the high CO₂ intensity of coal-fired BF supports the early competitiveness of DRI. Switching from NG-DRI to H2-DRI is even more dependent on the hydrogen price, as the CO₂ price has a lower impact resulting from a reduced CO₂ intensity of NG-DRI of about 68% compared to BF. High hydrogen prices increase avoidance costs to 180 to 260 €/tCO₂, delaying the break-even point to after 2035. However, hydrogen becomes attractive in all sensitivities before 2050, even with high hydrogen prices (Figure 5 (c)). The early competitiveness of NG-DRI helps the steel industry to avoid lock-ins, serving as an interim solution towards climate neutrality. Once hydrogen is competitive and available in sufficient quantities, it can replace natural gas without significant additional investments.

Similarly to the NG-DRI to H2-DRI transition, for ammonia production, the hydrogen prices significantly impact the break-even point (Figure 6 (a)). In both cases, the cost difference between natural gas and hydrogen is the main determinant. A different situation is observed for HVC and methanol production. Converting methanol production to the direct use of green hydrogen is only competitive with low hydrogen prices and high CO₂ prices, resulting in a late break-even point, which is even after 2050 in some sensitivities (Figure 6 (b)). This effect is even more pronounced for the conversion of HVC (Figure 6 (c)), where the

switch from naphtha-based steam crackers to MtHVC using climate-neutral methanol becomes cost-competitive only after 2043 at the lowest hydrogen prices. In both cases (methanol and HVC) a large share of the fossil carbon is bound as a raw material and embedded in the product rather than emitted during production, which limits the impact of the CO₂ price. Under current EU Emissions Trading rules, the respective chemical companies do not need CO₂ allowances for the carbon embedded in their products [30]. The resulting emissions occur at a later point in the value chain, such as during waste incineration.

To conclude, the combination of the high impact of the CO₂ price on coal-fired blast furnaces and the availability of a transitional process with NG-DRI helps to mitigate the risk of fossil lock-ins in the primary steel production. In contrast, the analysis of cost competitiveness shows that especially hydrogen-based alternatives for methanol and HVC will not be cost competitive in the medium term and require both a high CO₂ price and a low hydrogen price. It is very likely that hydrogen-based alternatives will not yet be competitive when reinvestments are required in the coming decade, and the pressure to reinvest in fossil fuel-based processes will be very high. Avoiding fossil lock-ins here will require additional policy measures.

3.2. Market diffusion results

The temporal dynamics as well as the spatial resolution and the impact of the planned hydrogen infrastructure on the plant-specific market diffusion of hydrogen-based processes are analysed.

3.2.1. Temporal dynamics

The results for the technical reinvestment cycles (section 3.1.1) and the competitiveness of hydrogen-based processes (section 3.1.2) determine the technology diffusion across the 16 sensitivities defined. The sensitivities vary in terms of the price for hydrogen and CO₂, which affects the economic viability of the various reinvestment options. Figure 7 shows the technology diffusion over time for all price combinations and aggregated for the four products considered. The vertical axis of rising CO₂ price leads to earlier diffusion and higher shares of hydrogen-based processes, while falling prices for climate-neutral hydrogen on the horizontal axis have an even stronger impact. However, this effect may change with different hydrogen and CO₂ price paths. Low CO₂ and high hydrogen prices result in late and low diffusion of hydrogen-based processes from around 2040 onwards, with NG-DRI taking early large production shares due to lower emissions compared

Fig. 5. CO₂ avoidance costs for primary steel (BF vs. NG-DRI (a), BF vs. H2-DRI (b), and NG-DRI vs. H2-DRI (c)) production in the four different hydrogen price sensitivities and comparison to the four defined CO₂ price paths

Fig. 6. CO₂ avoidance costs for chemicals (ammonia (a), methanol (b) and HVC (c)) production in the four different hydrogen price sensitivities and comparison to the four defined CO₂ price paths

to blast furnaces. For the lowest CO₂ and highest hydrogen price sensitivity, the switch from natural gas to hydrogen remains incomplete until 2050. In contrast, the share of H₂-DRI increases drastically with increasing CO₂ prices and decreasing hydrogen prices according to the avoidance cost curves from Figure 5 (c) up to nearly 100% diffusion of hydrogen-based processes.

Higher CO₂ prices also accelerate the diffusion of hydrogen-based ammonia production. However, in case of the high hydrogen price sensitivity, even with the highest CO₂ price path, hydrogen only supplies about 50% of the entire plant stock. The remaining plants already reinvested in (SMR) using natural gas, which are assumed to operate for 25 years. Lower hydrogen prices lead to earlier and higher shares of hydrogen-based ammonia production of up to nearly 80%.

For MthVc and climate-neutral methanol, the high and medium-high hydrogen price paths prevent hydrogen diffusion, even with high CO₂ prices. Climate-neutral methanol shows low shares of 15–30% by 2050 for the medium-low hydrogen price sensitivities and reaches 65% at low hydrogen prices. Similarly, low hydrogen prices start the slow diffusion of hydrogen-based HVC production, which reaches shares of 20 to 40% by 2050. Thus, conventional steam crackers persist until 2050 regardless of price variations due to the high demand for hydrogen and the low impact of the CO₂ price. Overall, comparing the diffusion dynamics shows that full market diffusion by 2050 is unlikely even under a broad range of economic assumptions if the natural reinvestment cycle remains unchanged. This is particularly valid for the chemical processes that switch from fossil feedstock to hydrogen and have a large proportion of the carbon embedded in the products.

To better understand these diffusion patterns, it's essential to examine reinvestments in fossil processes. Figure 8 compares the individual products for two selected sensitivities both showing a linear increase of the CO₂ price from 80 €/tCO₂ in 2022 to 300 €/tCO₂ in 2050: Sensitivity 5 (highest hydrogen price path: 57 €/GJ in 2022 to 30 €/GJ in 2050) and sensitivity 8 (lowest hydrogen price path: 27 €/GJ in 2022 to 15 €/GJ in 2050).

Figure 8 shows both the total production shares and new annual investment in tons per process. This illustrates the long-term effects of early reinvestments in fossil processes, which are still operating in 2050 thereby perpetuating a fossil-based production system. Fossil lock-in reinvestments are lowest for steel, although there are still a few investments in blast furnaces until 2031. These are, however, replaced by DRI in the second reinvestment cycle. The diffusion of H₂-DRI depends strongly on the hydrogen price. While NG-DRI shows high shares until 2045 in sensitivity 5, the stock is dominated by H₂-DRI from the

beginning in sensitivity 8. For the basic chemical products, Figure 8 shows larger shares of fossil reinvestments. Sensitivity 5 is completely dominated by reinvestments in fossil processes, most of which operate until 2050. In comparison, sensitivity 8 shows substantial investments in climate-neutral processes due to its low hydrogen price path, with the highest market share for ammonia among the basic chemicals. However, there are still reinvestments in fossil SMR throughout the entire period until 2050. Here, the limited access to hydrogen infrastructure partly results in avoiding the use of hydrogen (see section 3.2.2).

For HVC, investments in fossil-based steam crackers dominate until 2050, with a few hydrogen-based MthVc investments appearing mainly after 2045, resulting in a 20% market share. A similar trend is observed for methanol but ending in higher shares of climate-neutral production of around 60%. Across all products, the results indicate that the substantial share of investments required in the near future put considerable pressure on the industry.

For steel, around 90% of blast furnace capacity requires relining between 2025 and 2040. In the basic chemicals plant stock, 41% of steam cracker capacity, 22% of ammonia capacity and 51% of methanol capacity will reach their end of life before 2030. Thus, policy makers need to quickly establish an economic framework that encourages a switch to climate-neutral processes. Bridging processes like NG-DRI, which significantly reduce CO₂ emissions, enable a transition to climate-neutral hydrogen once it becomes available at competitive prices and avoid fossil lock-ins.

3.2.2. Regional resolution and hydrogen transport infrastructure

Figure 9 illustrates the spatial distribution of all considered plants. The size of each bubble represents the cumulative energy demand across all energy carriers at each site in 2022. HVC sites have the highest consumption due to high feedstock use, followed by primary steel sites, ammonia, and methanol. Northwest Europe, including western Germany, the Netherlands and Belgium shows the highest density of industrial plants and energy demand. Central and eastern Europe also have a comparatively dense heavy industry landscape compared to the north and south. Appendix F shows the spatial and temporal development of the energy demand for each energy carrier for sensitivity 16. Hydrogen demand and its distribution are limited by infrastructure constraints and the plans of the EHB consortium. Early industry transformation towards hydrogen use starts in the region including western Germany, the Netherlands and Belgium at primary steel manufacturing sites and some ammonia plants by 2030. By 2040, primary steel transformation is nearly complete, expanding towards the eastern Europe and

Fig. 7. Share of total production per process depending on hydrogen and CO₂-prices (Fig. 3). Hydrogen prices variate per column according to defined price paths from Fig. 3 (a). CO₂-prices variate per row according to defined price paths from Fig. 3 (b)

the first HVC and methanol plants start operating with hydrogen. Between 2040 and 2050, several HVC plants are replaced by MthVC, in line with a strong increase in hydrogen use across Europe as well as an almost complete substitution of ammonia plants.

Figure 10 compares sensitivity 16 (a) with a variation where investment behaviour is not restricted by the consideration of hydrogen infrastructure (b). The spatial and process-related difference (c) indicates that hydrogen-based processes are not chosen at some sites because of the missing connection to hydrogen infrastructure, especially in Scandinavian countries and France.

In southern Italy, HVC sites must make investment decisions before accessing hydrogen infrastructure (d), leading to fossil production lock-ins. For a total of 16 sites, the absence of hydrogen infrastructure when

investment decisions are made increases the likelihood of fossil re-investments. The other plants not investing in hydrogen-based processes until 2050 are stuck in lock-in investments for economic reasons.

3.3. Impacts of market diffusion

Following, the impact of the market diffusion and switch towards hydrogen-based processes on the energy demand, and more specifically the hydrogen demand as well as corresponding investments and emission mitigation are analysed.

3.3.1. Energy demand

The diffusion of hydrogen-based processes dependent on hydrogen

Fig. 8. Total production capacity and annual new investments by product and process

and CO₂ prices leads to varying energy demand per energy carrier in the sensitivities.

In 2022, coal (23%), natural gas (27%) and naphtha (42%) dominate the final demand, including feedstock, in EU27+3 for the considered products. Based on the share of total production per process from Figure 7, the sensitivities in Figure 11 shows that low CO₂ prices and high hydrogen prices result in high natural gas usage, no decrease in naphtha, and minimal hydrogen use for a few ammonia plants and H₂-DRI by 2050. However, these conditions still lead to a complete phase-out of coal use in blast furnaces, as NG-DRI is competitive.

The higher the CO₂ price and the lower the hydrogen price, the more the share of natural gas decreases over time and is replaced by hydrogen. This effect is driven by the economic shift from NG-DRI to H₂-DRI and the increasing hydrogen use for ammonia production. Hydrogen as a feedstock for HVC production is only able to compete with naphtha at very low hydrogen prices, as the CO₂ price has a limited effect due to the comparatively small quantities of natural gas used energetically in steam crackers. High CO₂ prices and low hydrogen prices in Germany make MthVC competitive from late 2043 (Figure 6 (c)), resulting in early lock-in investments. Despite optimistic assumptions, substantial amounts of

natural gas (~150 TWh) and naphtha (~ 50 TWh) remain in 2050.

Overall, the final energy demand decreases in all sensitivities, mainly as a result from switching in primary steel production to DRI process, which consumes less energy than blast furnaces. Using hydrogen in DRI is more efficient than using natural gas, so higher shares of H₂-DRI further reduce final energy demand in primary steel production. The detailed development for single products and countries is provided in the supplementary material.

3.3.2. Diffusion of hydrogen demand per product

None of the conducted sensitivities leads to a complete adoption of hydrogen-based processes for all products (Figure 7). However, hydrogen demand varies significantly by factor 8, ranging from 64 TWh to 507 TWh.

Figure 12 indicates that a higher CO₂ price and a lower hydrogen price trigger an earlier hydrogen ramp-up and increasing shares of hydrogen until 2050. The penalty from CO₂ prices on the emissions from the energetic use of natural gas in steam crackers is insufficient to achieve market diffusion of the MthVC process at medium to high hydrogen prices. Low naphtha prices and the ineffectiveness of the CO₂

Fig. 9. Locations of primary steel, HVC, ammonia and methanol plants in Europe sized by their current final energy demand.

price on fossil feedstock consumption lead to economic advantages for fossil steam crackers. However, for low hydrogen and high CO₂ prices, 20 of the 47 HVC plants may reinvest in MtHVC and these account for about 280 TWh of total hydrogen demand in 2050. This indicates that the EU's future hydrogen demand is highly sensitive to development and

investment decisions in HVC production, if no intermediates like methanol or other synthetic energy carriers are imported for these purposes. If all steam cracker plants adopted the MtHVC process, total hydrogen demand could reach around 1000 TWh.

3.3.3. Investments

The analysis of total investments per process in Figure 13 shows the expected outcome based on the production shares from Figure 7. The need to reinvest for blast furnaces follows a roughly linear trend and leads to investment decisions for around 70% of all primary steel plants until 2037.

Low CO₂ prices and high hydrogen prices provoke earlier process switching in primary steel plants and substantial investments in NG-DRI, which is, however, flexible in using hydrogen instead of natural gas. Interestingly, high CO₂ prices trigger more early investments in NG-DRI than low CO₂ prices. The higher CO₂ prices trigger early NG-DRI investments instead of blast furnace relining, which leads to a higher share of DRI in the early years. The second major investment block is the renewal of the EU's steam cracker plants. Some older steam cracker plants require early investment, and a second huge investment phase starts from 2035 onwards. Even with very low hydrogen and high CO₂ prices, investments in MtHVC only become attractive compared to conventional steam crackers around 2040 at the earliest. This is when more than 50% of the conventional steam cracker plants already required reinvestment based on their typical lifetime. All sensitivities also show lock-in investments for ammonia and methanol plants, as the hydrogen and CO₂ prices make hydrogen-based production economically unattractive or hydrogen from the EHB is not available in time.

Overall, the investments in ammonia and methanol production are nearly negligible compared to those in primary steel and HVC production. For ammonia, only small investments for ASU and Haber-Bosch adjustments are necessary, as hydrogen is expected to be supplied via pipeline. Methanol has only small capacities in the EU27+3 and specific investments are lower than for primary steel or HVC plants.

3.3.4. Greenhouse gas emissions

Low CO₂ prices and high hydrogen prices contribute to the continued use of coal through reinvestments in conventional blast furnaces and an increased reliance on natural gas in NG-DRI and chemicals production, as depicted in Figure 14. Thus, for low CO₂ and high hydrogen prices, emissions are only reduced by 10% until 2030 and by 55% until 2050. Higher CO₂ prices lead to a faster phase-out of coal and its related

Fig. 10. Spatial distribution of the resulting hydrogen demand of sensitivity 16 in 2050 considering the dependence on hydrogen infrastructure according to EHB plans (a), without considering the availability of hydrogen infrastructure for the investment decision (b), and the difference in hydrogen demand and its spatial distribution without (c) and with (d) displaying the respective infrastructures.

Fig. 11. Share of final energy demand (including feedstock demand) depending on hydrogen and CO₂ prices (Fig. 3).

emissions, while lower hydrogen prices have a smaller effect on the early replacement of blast furnaces. However, lower hydrogen prices do lead to the earlier substitution of natural gas as an energy source and therefore lower emissions. In general, high CO₂ prices lead to an almost complete phase-out of coal use until 2043, while process-related emissions from DRI and natural gas use in steam crackers account for 16% in the most optimistic sensitivity.

Thus, the reduction of energy-related CO₂ emissions varies between 55% and 84% in the sensitivity analyses.

4. Discussion

4.1. Potential role of other mitigation options

While this paper focuses on the framework needed for hydrogen-based processes, other mitigation options like electrification, CCU/S, or biomass will certainly also play a role in the future decarbonisation of the steel and chemicals industries [63]. These were not included in the quantitative modelling but are discussed here. Applying CCU/S at blast furnaces could mitigate CO₂ by only 20-40% [64]. When making retrofit investments for top gas recycling blast furnaces, capture rates may be improved up to around 50-70% [65]. While the costs for the emitted CO₂ would decrease with higher capture rates, additional costs for the

Fig. 12. Share of hydrogen demand per product (including feedstock demand) depending on hydrogen and CO₂ prices (Fig. 3).

capture technology and energy are required and remaining emissions would need to be compensated [66]. Direct electrification of primary steel production is currently not technically mature and unlikely to play a significant role in the near future [67]. Secondary steel production is limited by scrap availability but is likely to increase in the future as it is much more energy-efficient than primary production. This would reduce the potential demand for H₂-DRI. However, even if the above options emerge, H₂-DRI is still reckoned to be the major technology for future clean steel production [68], also because industry has already made decisions in this direction. Most European steel projects focus either on hydrogen or electrification [69]. Reviews on clean primary steel production also show huge activities in Europe and Asia [70].

CCU/S is also an option for ammonia production [71]. Some of the

CO₂ produced is already being captured and utilised today at individual sites with integrated urea production [72]. Similar to blast furnaces, it is not possible to capture all the emissions and additional investments in CCU/S technology, transport and storage or use would be needed. Electrochemical options like solid state ammonia synthesis are not yet technically mature or cost-competitive [73].

Research on electrifying steam cracker furnaces is ongoing, but the technology is still in its early stages and its large-scale integration remains uncertain [74]. Once available on industrial scale, it might be competitive using synthetic climate-neutral feedstock in the long-term.

The production of HVC and methanol requires a carbon source, currently provided by fossil fuels. In the transition to hydrogen-based processes, CO₂ will therefore play an important role [75]. The analysis

Fig. 13. Total investments per process due to process switch depending on hydrogen and CO₂ prices (Fig. 3).

does not specify the carbon source for methanol and HVC production via MtHVC, but hard-to-abate process-related emissions from cement or lime production could serve as a carbon source, possibly reducing costs in CO₂ emitting branches [76]. Waste incineration plants, included in EU ETS regulations from 2028 [77], will face economic pressure to avoid CO₂ emissions, with captured CO₂ either stored or used in industry. However, using fossil emissions as carbon feedstock necessitates closed carbon cycles or compensation to ensure climate neutrality [78]. Another often discussed option is direct air capture, though potentially more expensive, can achieve large-scale negative emissions. Current unclear boundary conditions and a lack of planning for CO₂ storage and

infrastructure make the future of CCU/S or other possible value chains difficult to predict. There are hardly any detailed plans or a regulatory framework for dealing with CCU/S at present, but it is important to closely consider the interplay between a hydrogen and carbon economy. In February 2024, the European Commission released a first draft towards an industrial carbon management that aims to establish a cooperation platform, identify demand, and promote corresponding value chains. [79]. Biomass as a feedstock for basic chemicals is another option, but its availability may be insufficient to transform the entire chemical industry [80].

Fig. 14. Total emissions due to process switch depending on hydrogen and CO₂ prices (Fig. 3).

4.2. Effect of CO₂ pricing

The results show that NG-DRI becomes competitive with fossil blast furnaces for steel production, assuming CO₂ opportunity costs are considered in investment decisions and neglecting benchmarking. This indicates the significant role of NG-DRI in the transition and synergies with developing a hydrogen system. Among others, the conversion of ammonia production could be one of the beneficiaries of DRI and infrastructure investments. With hydrogen infrastructure access, direct hydrogen use becomes economically viable over time compared to syngas from SMR. The analysis follows the current definition of EU ETS for the effect of CO₂ pricing, considering only direct emissions (scope 1) [30]. Especially for HVC, the assumed range of CO₂ prices is insufficient

to make hydrogen-based feedstock competitive, as large amounts of fossil naphtha as a feedstock (scope 3) are not affected by the CO₂ price. Additional measures, such as blending quotas for synthetic aviation fuels (SAF) [81], subsidies for green energy sources, or a CO₂ tax on feedstock, will be necessary to address high fossil fuel consumption. Furthermore, demand-side policies promoting green lead markets could stimulate the transition to climate-neutral feedstock. It is crucial to consider the role of imports, their future development, origin, and corresponding regulation and labelling in this context.

4.3. Reflection of plant ages and average lifetimes

The key drivers for technology diffusion in this modelling approach

are the age distribution of the current plant fleet and the resulting typical average reinvestment cycles. However, assuming major reinvestments is always a simplification of reality; sites can be partially modernised, or reinvestments postponed. Reinvestment cycles are less accurate for chemical products than for primary steel production due to regular maintenance, modernisation and incremental improvements to increase efficiency and avoid downtime [82]. In addition, the lower temperatures compared to steel lead to longer material lifetimes in chemical plants. Theoretical lifetimes for basic chemicals should therefore be seen more as modernisation cycles rather than reinvestment cycles. However, these modernisation costs still account for high cost shares [83] and can determine the decision for new investments.

For primary steel production, reinvestments are more discrete, making this approach is more accurate [41]. Despite uncertainties in distinct reinvestment cycles, older plants generally require more reinvestment and modernization than newer ones, validating the use of reinvestment cycles to capture such patterns. The results show that basically each plant has one large investment decision until 2050 to avoid lock-ins [84].

4.4. Structure of global value chains

The shown variations on future hydrogen demand from 64 to 507 TWh occur from the uncertainties in future hydrogen prices and depend on economic factors. Early reinvestments (e.g. driven by additional external factors like policies) before the end of a plant's lifetime could increase hydrogen demand from the investigated 64 to 507 TWh in the sensitivities up to 1000 TWh for the considered products [18]. However, the analyses reflect today's industry structure and value chains within Europe, without considering potential restructuring of global value chains, such as importing intermediate or end products. Prioritising different processes or establishing alternative value chains could lead to different developments. Recent studies have started to consider importing intermediate products, such as hot briquetted iron (HBI) for primary steel production [85]. In case of restructured value chains for the investigated products during the transition, it is essential to verify the robustness of hydrogen quantities and transport requirements to effectively construct a European hydrogen infrastructure. Other studies have already indicated the need for cross-country transport without drawing conclusions about individual pipelines or detailed changes in capacity [86].

4.5. The need for hydrogen infrastructure

The commissioning timelines for the individual hydrogen pipelines of the EHB initiative fit the calculated upcoming investments for most of the industry sites considered. For some sites illustrated in Figure 10, the planned commissioning year for the hydrogen pipelines could be too late or the pipeline is not close enough thus leading to lock-in investments in this analysis. Small shifts in the timing of investment decisions or adjustments to the plans for EHB could address this.

This alignment is expected for large industrial clusters, but the situation may differ for other sectors and smaller sites. These include the production of glass, ceramics, cement, lime, and metal products, which could all potentially use hydrogen to decarbonise production processes. Future research should extend the approach used in this paper to additional sectors beyond the major steel and chemical sites.

4.6. Summary

To achieve a sustainable transformation of the industry, it is essential to integrate infrastructure planning, the restructuring of global value chains, and circularity within the framework of a carbon and hydrogen economy. Various other barriers to industry decarbonisation have been identified and discussed alongside existing policies in the literature [87]. These interconnected aspects necessitate comprehensive consideration

and further research to understand the hurdles of industry decarbonisation. Here, a broad range of hydrogen price developments from literature had been used to investigate on the diffusion of hydrogen-based processes in the considered industry branches. This work and the developed approach can contribute to assessing decarbonisation options and transformation pathways. The insights and data provided can serve as basis for further research in energy system analysis and suitable policy measures.

5. Conclusions

Many studies expect industry to become the main hydrogen consumer in the future, although there is still substantial uncertainty about the dynamics and concrete pathways. This paper investigates the spatial and temporal dynamics of technology diffusion for primary steel, ammonia, HVC, and methanol using a plant-specific simulation model. The model considers the existing European plant stock and includes their georeferenced location, individual plant ages, production capacities, and reinvestment cycles. Investment decisions are based on overall production costs, comparing hydrogen-based and fossil-based processes.

The analysis reveals that for all plants considered at least one investment opportunity remains until 2050, with 36% requiring reinvestment by 2030 and 58% by 2035. Only few might have a second reinvestment opportunity. The results indicate significant pressure on industry to reinvest in fossil processes. For steel, 90% of blast furnaces need relining between 2025 and 2040. For HVC, 41% of steam crackers will reach their end of life before 2030. Policymakers must create an economic framework supporting climate-neutral processes. This early need for reinvestment poses a high risk of locking in fossil fuel-based processes before climate-neutral hydrogen supply can be established. Bridging processes like NG-DRI, which reduce CO₂ emissions immediately and later switch to hydrogen, should be exploited to avoid fossil lock-ins.

To understand the impact of economic factors, 16 defined sensitivities vary hydrogen and CO₂ prices. The results show that the economic competitiveness of climate-neutral processes heavily depends on hydrogen prices, which are uncertain. However, the economic viability also varies strongly among the products and processes. Hydrogen-based alternatives for methanol and HVC are not cost-competitive in the medium term and require low hydrogen prices as CO₂ prices have a weak impact as most carbon is embedded in products rather than emitted during production. Enhancing the competitiveness of climate-neutral processes to produce HVC, methanol and ammonia is substantial in the short and medium term to avoid reinvestments in fossil-based processes. For steel, the combination of a high CO₂ price impact on coal-fired blast furnaces and the availability of transitional natural gas-based direct reduction of iron ore (NG-DRI) mitigates the risk of fossil lock-ins. Full market diffusion by 2050 across the products is unlikely if natural reinvestment cycles remain unchanged, especially for chemical processes switching from fossil feedstock to hydrogen.

Assuming that the structure and spatial distribution of European industry remains similar to today, the highest hydrogen demand will be in Northwestern Europe, including Germany, the Netherlands and Belgium. Sensitivity 16, which shows the highest hydrogen demand, shows around 39 TWh for 2030 and 229 TWh for 2050 in those regions out of 64 TWh for 2030 and 507 TWh for 2050 in EU27+3, respectively. These estimates consider plant ages, reinvestment cycles and infrastructure availability, but not specific investment plans or government subsidies. However, the market diffusion remains incomplete, and the total technical potential is about 1000 TWh in the EU27+3, assuming constant production volumes.

The plant-specific market diffusion is calculated in dependence of hydrogen infrastructure according to the EHB with a proximity of 30 km. Only 16 sites will require reinvestment before the planned hydrogen infrastructure is operating or have no access within this proximity.

Here, hydrogen-based processes are examined in isolation. Future

research should consider and analyse the competition with alternative climate-neutral processes like direct electrification, biomass or carbon capture, especially for those plants without access to hydrogen infrastructure. In addition, a better understanding is required of potential changes in value chains, including imports of intermediate energy-intensive products [88], or the renewables pull effect [89], and this calls for investigations from a global perspective. In addition, the approach can be used next to assess how well the planned hydrogen or other infrastructure fits the needs of other energy-intensive industries like glass, ceramics or metal processing.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marius Neuwirth: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tobias Fleiter:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **René Hofmann:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A.: Process diffusion model

The behaviour of technology diffusion in industry differs from other areas where known diffusion theories try to reflect socio-economic behaviour. For example, the long life cycles and very high investments involved in industry lead to very specific points of time for reinvestment. Furthermore, bad investments entail an enormous risk in terms of loss of economic competitiveness. In most cases, energy costs account for the biggest proportion of total production costs (TCOP). Apart from economic aspects, aspects like the availability of energy carriers and the corresponding infrastructure also determine investment decisions in industry. On the other hand, investment decisions in industry are much more rational and cost-benefit based than they are for consumers. To sum up, technology diffusion in industrial stock is strongly dependent on the plant age and lifetime of current processes as well as the cost-effectiveness and competitiveness of the investment options.

Based on this context, the model initialises each industrial site. Investments in new processes are made according to reinvestment cycles calculated based on the specific age and process lifetime of each site. The industry sites decide separately for each plant which process is the most economic investment for the upcoming life cycle by comparing the TCOP of all alternatives (equation (1)). The alternatives can be limited depending on the availability of energy carriers in the respective region and distance to necessary infrastructure or by applying a technology ban.

$$Inv_p = \min(TCOP) \quad (1)$$

Inv_p process with lowest TCOP evaluated for new investment for the individual plant

$TCOP$ total cost of production (TCOP)

The total cost of production per process is calculated from the total specific production cost per process multiplied by the annual output of the plant (equation (2)).

$$TCOP = c_p \cdot o_{pu} \quad (2)$$

c_p specific production costs per process available per plant

o_{pu} output in tons of yearly production per production unit

The specific production cost represents the sum of different cost components per ton of product, comprising the annuity on investment, operational costs, energy-related costs and external influences like penalties for emissions as well as subsidies or funding (equation (3)).

$$c_p = c_a + c_o + c_{ec} + c_{ext} \quad (3)$$

c_p specific total cost per ton of product

c_a specific annuity on investment per ton of product

c_o specific operational costs per ton of product

c_{ec} specific energy carrier costs per ton of product

c_{ext} external influences on specific total cost per ton of product

Data availability

Most important data (model input, industry site information, result files) are shared as [supplementary material](#) as open data. Any further data will be made available upon request.

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Appendix B: Number of sites and plants per country

Appendix B1 shows the detailed number of plants per product and process for each country.

There is additional information for all of these sites on company affiliation, geocoordinates, emissions and related plants on site level as well as production capacity, process and plant age on plant level. A more detailed resolution is provided in the [supplementary material S1_2](#).

Appendix B1: Number of manufacturing sites and plants per product and process in Europe for basic chemicals and primary steel production per country covered in this analysis.

Country	Number of	Steel, primary		Olefins	Ammonia	Methanol	Sum
		BF/BOF	NG-DRI/EAF	Steam cracker	Steam reforming	Steam reforming	
AT	Sites	2		1	1		4
	Plants	5		1	2		8
BE	Sites	1		2	2		5
	Plants	2		3	2		7
BG	Sites				1		1
	Plants				1		1
CZ	Sites	2		1	1		4
	Plants	4		1	1		6
DE	Sites	7	1	9	4	4	25
	Plants	15	1	14	6	4	40
EE	Sites				1		1
	Plants				1		1
EL	Sites				1		1
	Plants				1		1
ES	Sites	1		3	2		6
	Plants	2		3	2		7
FI	Sites	1		1			2
	Plants	2		1			3
FR	Sites	3		6	4		13
	Plants	8		6	4		18
HR	Sites				1		1
	Plants				1		1
HU	Sites	1		1	1		3
	Plants	1		2	1		4
IT	Sites	1		2	1		4
	Plants	3		2	1		6
LT	Sites				1		1
	Plants				2		2
NL	Sites	1		3	1	1	6
	Plants	2		6	5	2	15
NO	Sites			1	1	1	3
	Plants			1	1	1	3
PL	Sites	2		1	5		8
	Plants	3		1	8		12
PT	Sites			1			1
	Plants			1			1
RO	Sites	1			2		3
	Plants	1			2		3
SE	Sites	2		1			3
	Plants	3		1			4
SK	Sites	1		1	1		3
	Plants	3		1	1		5
UK	Sites	2		3	3		8
	Plants	4		3	3		10
Sum	Sites	28	1	37	34	6	96*
	Plants	58	1	47	45	7	158

* Some of the chemicals plants are located at the same site. Thus, the number of sites in this table do not add up to 96 when counted separately.

Appendix B2 shows the manually derived sources for steam cracker plants.

Appendix B2: Sources from manual search for steam cracker plants

Country	Company	Website
General Information: https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Liste_der_Erd%C3%B6lraffinerien		
AT	OMV/Borealis	https://www.borealisgroup.com/company/history ; https://www.omv.com/services/downloads/00/omv.com/1522207986091/dload_ir_Factbook2020_EN_DE
BE	TOA	https://totalenergies.com/media/news/press-releases/belgium-total-completes-the-upgrade-of-its-largest-refining-and-petrochemicals-platform-in-europe
BE	BASF	https://www.basf.com/global/images/about-us/history/BASF_Chronik_Gesamt_en.pdf.assetdownload.pdf ; https://www.basf.com/be/en/who-we-are/Group-Companies/BASF-Antwerpen/About-the-site/History.html#accordion_v2-d72a3ed53c-item-cd0f64125b ; https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/geoasset-project/petrochemicals/
BE	Sabic Europe	https://2b1stconsulting.com/sabic-invests-170-million-in-geleen-naphtha-cracker/
NL	Shell	https://www.shell.com/business-customers/chemicals/media-releases/2020-media-releases/shell-invests-in-new-furnaces-to-reduce-emissions-from-its-moerdijk-chemicals-plant.html ; https://nl.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shell_Moerdijk ; https://www.shell.com/business-customers/chemicals/media-releases/2014-media-releases/shell-moerdijk-40-years.html
BE	Dow	https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/geoasset-project/petrochemicals/

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Country	Company	Website
CZ	Unipetrol	https://www.linde-engineering.com/en/about-linde-engineering/success-stories/rescue-plan-for-refinery.html ; https://www.process.vogel.de/wie-linde-einen-zerstoerten-unipetrol-steamcracker-wieder-aufbaut-a-634912/ ; https://www.unipetrol.cz/en/AboutUs/Pages/History.aspx
FI	Borealis	https://www.borealisgroup.com/company/history ; https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/geoasset-project/petrochemicals/ ; https://www.omv.com/services/downloads/00/omv.com/1522207986091/dload_ir_Factbook2020_EN_DE
FR	LyondellBasell	https://www.lyondellbasell.com/en/about-us/history/ ; https://new.societechimiquedefrance.fr/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/b_9_000_000.vf3-sav.pdf
FR	Versalis	https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Liste_der_Erd%C3%B6lraffinerien
FR	A.P. Feyzin	https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/geoasset-project/petrochemicals/
FR	Total	http://www.beyond3d.com.au/uploads/9/1/6/8/9168625/035.pdf ; https://totalenergies.com/system/files/documents/2022-03/DEU_21_VA.pdf
FR	Naphtachimie	https://new.societechimiquedefrance.fr/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/b_9_000_000.vf3-sav.pdf
FR	ExxonMobil	https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Liste_der_Erd%C3%B6lraffinerien
DE	Dow	https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/7067/file/7067_Low-carbon-Industrie.pdf
DE	OMV/Borealis	https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/7067/file/7067_Low-carbon-Industrie.pdf
DE	BP	https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/7067/file/7067_Low-carbon-Industrie.pdf
DE	Klesch	https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/7067/file/7067_Low-carbon-Industrie.pdf
DE	Ineos Olefins	https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/7067/file/7067_Low-carbon-Industrie.pdf
DE	BASF	https://www.basf.com/global/images/about-us/history/BASF_Chronik_Gesamt_en.pdf.assetdownload.pdf ; https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/7067/file/7067_Low-carbon-Industrie.pdf
DE	LyondellBasell	https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/7067/file/7067_Low-carbon-Industrie.pdf
DE	Shell	https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/7067/file/7067_Low-carbon-Industrie.pdf
HU	MOL	https://molgroup.info/en/our-business/downstream/production-sites
IT	Versalis	https://www.chemanager-online.com/en/news/petchems-age-porto-marghera-may-really-end
NO	Ineos Olefins	https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/geoasset-project/petrochemicals/
PL	PKN Orlen	http://abarrelfull.wikidot.com/plock-refinery ; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/P%C5%82ock_refinery
PT	Repsol	https://www.ordemengenhaires.pt/fotos/editor2/regiaosul/oe_repsol_polimeros_site_21nov2018.pdf
SL	MOL	https://molgroup.info/en/our-business/downstream/production-sites
ES	Repsol	https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/geoasset-project/petrochemicals/ ; https://www.k-online.com/en/Media_News/News/Repsol_restarts_its_Tarragona_cracker_1
ES	Dow	https://digital.library.mcgill.ca/images/hrcoreports/pdfs/6/636970.pdf ; https://www.spglobal.com/pdf/RW2014-13-toc_214324110917062932.pdf ; https://ekj-co.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/REFERENCE-LIST-2019-Nacional.pdf ; https://ence.uz/Reference_list_2012.pdf
SE	Borealis	https://www.borealisgroup.com/company/history ; https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/geoasset-project/petrochemicals/
UK	Ineos Olefins	https://www.chemistryworld.com/news/grangemouth-will-switch-to-shale-gas-feed-by-2016-says-ineos/7223.article ; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Grangemouth_Refinery
UK	ExxonMobil	https://www.exxonmobil.co.uk/News/Newsroom/UK-News-releases/2019/0917_ExxonMobil-announces-further-investment-at-Fife-Ethylene-Plant ; https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/geoasset-project/petrochemicals/
UK	Sabik UK	http://www.mrcplast.com/news-news_open-395021.html ; https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/geoasset-project/petrochemicals/ ; https://www.sabic-teesside.co.uk/en/teesside-site/wilton-site ; https://www.icis.com/explore/resources/news/2021/10/28/10699571/sabic-s-wilton-uk-cracker-to-restart-after-850m-investment-could-run-on-hydrogen/

Appendix B3 shows the manually derived sources for ammonia plants.

Appendix B3: Sources from manual search for ammonia plants.

Country	Company	Website
General Information: https://eippcb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2019-11/lvic_aaf.pdf		
AT	Borealis Agrolinz Melamine	https://www.borealisgroup.com/about-us/history
BE	YARA Belgium	https://www.yara.com/siteassets/investors/057-reports-and-presentations/other/2020/production-capacities-by-segment-september-2020-pdf.pdf ; https://www.yara.nl/fr-be/a-propos-de-yara/yara-tertre/information/
BE	BASF Antwerp	https://www.basf.com/be/en/who-we-are/Group-Companies/BASF-Antwerpen/About-the-site/History.html#accordion_v2-d72a3ed53c-item-cd0f64125b
CZ	ORLEN Unipetrol	https://www.unipetrol.cz/en/AboutUs/Pages/History.aspx ; https://chemicalparks.eu/news/orlen-unipetrol-ammonia-production-modernization
EE	OSTCHEM Nitrofert Estonia	http://www.ostchem.com/en/o-kompanii/proizvodstvo/nitrofert
FR	Borealis	https://www.borealisgroup.com/about-us/history
FR	Yara France	https://www.yara.fr/a-propos-yara/nos-implantations/
NL	OCI	https://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/o/oci_2017.pdf ; https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/pbl-2019-decarbonisation-options-for-the-dutch-fertiliser-industry_3657.pdf
LT	Achema Lithuania	https://www.chema.lt/history
PL	Grupa Azoty	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/295603303_New_plant_for_neutralization_of_nitric_acid_with_ammonia_in_Grupa_Azoty_Zaklady_Azotowe_Kedzierzyn_Operational_experience ; https://tarnow.grupaazoty.com/en/the-company/about-the-company/history
RO	Chemgas	https://ji.unfccc.int/UserManagement/FileStorage/Q3MP4NYSEJCSUF28LTGXR70Z9HWOA ; https://www.enpg.ro/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Decarbonising_Romanias_Industry_Policy_Paper_updated_EPG.pdf
RO	InterAgro	https://www.romania-insider.com/donau-chem-reopening-jun-2020 ; https://seenews.com/news/interagro-reopens-donau-chem-fertilizer-plant-in-southern-romania-704511 ; https://www.enpg.ro/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Decarbonising_Romanias_Industry_Policy_Paper_updated_EPG.pdf
UK	Severnside	https://www.theconstructionindex.co.uk/news/view/4500-tonne-uk-ammonia-plant-dismantled-for-reassembly-overseas
DE	Ineos	https://www.ineoskoeln.de/unternehmen/herkunft/
DE	BASF	https://www.basf.com/se/en/media/news-releases/20201/10/p-21-355.html
DE	Yara	https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yara-Werk_Brunsb%C3%BCttel
DE	SKW	https://www.skwp.de/unternehmen/unternehmensprofil/historie/ ; https://www.skwp.de/fileadmin/content/05_mediacenter/broschueren/umwelterklaerung/Aktualisierung-Umwelterklaerung_2017.pdf ; https://www.uni-kiel.de/anorg/lagaly/group/klausSchiver/piesteritz1.pdf

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Country	Company	Website
DE	BP Gelsenkirchen	
HU	Nitrogenművek	https://www.nitrogen.hu/hu/nitrogenmuvek-idovonal ; https://bjj.hu/business/industry/manufacturing/nitrogenmuvek-restarts-ammonia-production
PL	Grupa Azoty Pulawy	https://pulawy.grupaazoty.com/en/the-company/about-the-company/history/history-in-the-years#60-s
PL	Grupa Azoty Kedzierzyn	https://zak.grupaazoty.com/spolka/o-firmie/historia

Appendix B4 shows the manually derived sources for methanol

Appendix B4: Sources from manual search for methanol plants.

Country	Company	Website
DE	BASF	https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2021/Jan/IRENA_Innovation_Renewable_Methanol_2021.pdf ; https://www.basf.com/global/documents/de/about-us/history/History-in-Figures/1965-1989/1978_BASF_Geschaeftsbericht.pdf
DE	Total	https://www.deutsches-chemie-museum.de/datei/anzeigen/id/4131,1089/mb_11_1998_3_erdoel_schmierstoffe.pdf ; https://www.mz.de/lokal/merseburg/spergau-leben-mit-der-raffinerie-2407613 ; https://www.process.vogel.de/richtfest-in-leuna-a-58386/
DE	Ruhr Oel	https://www.bp.com/de_de/germany/home/wo-wir-sind/raffinerie-gelsenkirchen/wer-wir-sind/zahlen-und-fakten.html ; https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/country-sites/de_de/germany/home/unsere-raffinerien/raffinerie-gelsenkirchen/publikationen/ausgaben-2022/2022-12-gemeinsam-nachbarschaftszeitung.pdf
DE	Shell	https://s06.static-shell.com/content/dam/royaldutchshell/documents/corporate/manufacturing-rhinelandhistory.pdf
NO	Statoil	https://www.equinor.com/news/archive/202102-tjeldbergodden ; https://www.tbu.no/en/ressurser/
NL	BioMCN	https://oci-global.com/news-stories/stories/oci-global-explores-sustainable-methanol-in-delfzijl/ ; https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2021/Jan/IRENA_Innovation_Renewable_Methanol_2021.pdf

Appendix C.: Validation of industry site data

As an indicator, a comparison was made of the last complete and confirmed production quantities per product and country. Based on official sources, the completeness of production capacities of the developed Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase for the products considered was validated.

Primary steel capacities:

The World Steel Association [90] annually publishes national production volumes per product type and process, while Eurofer [32] and Global Steel Plant Tracker [33] serve as references for plant capacities of the iron and steel sector. Appendix C 1 shows the comparison of the national production volume of pig iron from blast furnaces and the capacities of the above-mentioned sources and the Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase. Overall, a very good match of plant capacities for blast furnaces and oxygen converters can be seen for all countries. This suggests a complete mapping of primary steel production for the modelling. Minor deviations between the sources can be validated by manual internet research on corresponding values of the database used for modelling.

Appendix C1: Primary steel production in 2021 [90] and comparison of primary steel capacities per country from Eurofer [32], Global Steel Plant Tracker [33] and Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase

Ethylene capacities (representative for HVC):

Appendix C2: Ethylene production in 2017 and 2019 from Prodcum [37] and NationMaster [91] and comparison with national capacity from Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase

In general, the data for chemicals production are not as readily available as for the iron and steel sector. Furthermore, value chains in the chemical sector are more complex and it is therefore harder to understand and collect detailed and comprehensive data. In case of high value chemicals (olefins and aromatics), the largest shares are produced in steam cracker plants in Europe by cracking naphtha that serves as a fossil feedstock.

As there are no statistics from any international association, **Appendix C 2** displays the comparison of national production volumes per country for 2017 and 2019 from Prodcum [37] and NationMaster [91] and collected plant capacities within Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase. However, especially for non-EU countries like Norway or the UK, it is difficult to gather information. Overall, the collected plant capacities match the respective national production and are complete for all the covered countries, with the exception of very small amounts in Bulgaria.

Ammonia capacities:

As already stated for HVC, gathering data on ammonia production plants in Europe was challenging in some cases. However, older grey literature and screening European chemical company websites led to a thorough dataset including information about plant age. As shown in **Appendix C 3**, comparing the annual production for 2017, 2019 and 2020 taken from Prodcum [37] with the data collected on production capacities indicates the completeness of Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase. Comparing the geospatial resolution of the collected sites and plants also shows conformity with other reports [36].

In a few cases (France, Germany, Lithuania, Poland, Spain), ammonia production capacity greatly exceeds production. This may result from direct urea production not being reported as ammonia manufacturing at specific sites in these countries or from low utilisation factors.

Appendix C3: Ammonia production in 2017, 2019 and 2020 from Prodcum [37] and comparison with national capacities from Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase

Methanol capacities:

While methanol is seen as playing a major role as an energy carrier and feedstock in future industrial value chains [92], current production capacities in Europe are small. Germany, the Netherlands and Norway account for the majority of European production [37]. However, due to the monopoly of the companies involved, there is no obligation to report any official statistics. The methanol plant in Romania was closed in 2021. Despite these obstacles, **Appendix C 4** indicates the completeness of the Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase for European methanol facilities.

Appendix C4: Methanol production in 2017 and 2019 from Prodcum [37] and comparison with national capacity from Fraunhofer ISI IndustrialSiteDatabase

Appendix D: Model validation

Apart from validating the data basis used for modelling, it is also crucial that model heuristics, calculations and results are reliable. However, validating such detailed data input and model results requires statistics of a similar granularity for comparison. Here, calibration of the plant-specific model input data is according to the production outputs presented in Appendix C. More precisely, to estimate the average production per plant, the national utilisation factor is applied per product, calculated by dividing the annual production by the available annual capacity per country. This assumption is simultaneously the restricting factor, which may lead to differences occurring between individual sites in each country, as it assumes a similar average load factor for each plant. Having calibrated the production output per plant, the modelled results of the calculated CO₂ emissions are compared with the emission reporting within the EU ETS [93] on a site and country-level for the respective year. The calculation within the model is based on the input data on the energy and steam demand per process and the corresponding shares of energy carrier use. The underlying emission factors (Table 3) for each energy carrier result in the calculated emissions per plant and site.

For the comparison, however, the level of detail for reported emissions in the EU ETS is not uniform. While some companies report one single value for all facilities at a site, others report individual values for each plant.

When comparing the results for the calculated emissions, indirectly also validation of the data and calculations of energy demand per energy carrier and other indicators is given, as these equations form the basis for the resulting plant-specific emissions.

Primary Steel:

For primary steel manufacturing sites, the site-level comparison is shown in Appendix D 1 (a) for 2021. The averaged utilisation factor per plant leads to differences between individual sites for each country (e.g. site 143 and 148 in Germany), which indicates that they operated with a different capacity utilisation. When aggregating those results to a country level (Appendix D 1 (b)), the calculated national emissions are a good match to the reported emissions within the EU ETS [93]. An exact match is neither expected nor manageable, as each plant differs in efficiency, degree of modernisation as well as process integration at large industry sites. Therefore, the aim is to reflect a realistic average, which can be proven and validated by these analyses. As the reporting within EU ETS also shows large inconsistencies, other installations had to be included in this comparison to allocate the facilities to the sites.

Appendix D1: Comparison of calculated emissions from primary steel production based on national production in 2021 from the model calculation and reported EU ETS emissions [93] per site (a) and country (b)

Ammonia:

When comparing the calculated emissions from ammonia production with EU ETS facilities, some plants cannot be covered as they are part of refinery sites or chemical parks that do not report at facility level. Appendix D 2 shows the comparison of the model results with identifiable emissions of single ammonia facilities as reported in the EU ETS. Steam methane reforming (SMR) with the respective techno-economic assumptions serves as a reference process for ammonia production in the model. As this process also covers the majority of ammonia plants operating in Europe, the emission comparison is a good match for most of the identified plants. However, larger differences occurred for individual plants, which can be explained by the fact that some use heavy oil to produce the required synthesis gas. The use of heavy oil results in higher energy demand as well as higher emission factors and around 30% higher emissions compared to SMR used as the reference process in the model. Especially for Germany and Lithuania, this seems to explain the differences.

(a)

(b)

Appendix D2: Comparison of calculated emissions from ammonia production based on national production from 2019 from the model calculation and reported EU ETS emissions [70] per site (a) and country (b)

Olefins:

Similar to ammonia plants, steam crackers for HVC production are partly located in huge chemical parks or refineries and are therefore not reported individually within the EU ETS. Refineries, in particular, do not report with a detailed resolution. Therefore, **Appendix D 3** shows a comparison excluding refinery sites. Steam cracking of naphtha is used as the reference process in the model for the techno-economic assumptions, which represents the most widely used process in Europe [94]. However, there are also uncertainties for HVC regarding the feedstock used and the degree of process integration within sites, e.g. for using excess heat. These uncertainties lead to some huge differences between sites and countries. Different plant ages, efficiencies, level of site integration and the utilisation factor applied mean that an exact match was not expected for individual plants and sites, but the comparison shows that the model results are validated within the expected variation.

(a)

(b)

Appendix D3: Comparison of calculated emissions from HVC production based on national production from 2019 from the model calculation and reported EU ETS emissions [70] per site (a) and country (b)

Methanol:

Methanol plants in Europe are mostly integrated in large refineries and not reported in the EU ETS as individual facilities, which results in enormous differences at site level (**Appendix D 4** (a)). The plants in the Netherlands and Norway are the exceptions. There is a good match with the emissions of methanol production in the Netherlands, while larger differences can be seen for the plant in Norway (**Appendix D 4** (b)). This could be explained by the use of biomass, for which emissions are not reported under the EU ETS, or the capture and re-use of CO₂ or the use of different feedstock, as SMR is taken as a reference for the production of synthesis gas in the model.

(a)

(b)

Appendix D4: Comparison of calculated emissions from methanol production based on national production from 2019 from the model calculation and reported EU ETS emissions [70] per site (a) and country (b)

Chemicals total:

When comparing the emissions for HVC, ammonia and methanol calculated by the model with those reported in the EU ETS, there is a good match for aggregated national figures excluding refinery sites (**Appendix D 5 (a)**) with relatively few deviations for each country. Germany, in particular, has comparably many steam cracker, ammonia and methanol plants located at refinery sites and this leads to an underestimation of their emissions by around 30% when including the whole emissions from refinery sites from EU ETS into the comparison.

Appendix D5: Comparison of calculated emissions from chemicals production based on national production from 2019 from the model calculation and reported EU ETS emissions [70] per site (a) and country (b)

Appendix E: Evaluation of reinvestment cycles

Uncertainties in anticipating reinvestment cycles arise from the site-specific and technical individuality of plants as well as the decision making of their owners concerning reinvestments and incremental improvements. Different types and scopes of measures to extend lifetimes also lead to postponed reinvestments that are difficult to anticipate. Thus, using theoretical reinvestment cycles based on statistics may deviate from the real-life point of investment. However, this approach draws a clearer picture of the possible transition pathways than the statistical diffusion theories used so far, especially due to the inclusion of the spatial component.

Primary steel (Blast furnaces):

Major reinvestment cycles in primary steel production are predetermined by the blast furnace campaign life. Renewal of the refractory lining and cooling units is crucial within such a relining. The literature often states lifetimes of 15-25 years for blast furnaces [40]. An analysis by Vogl et al. [41] estimated the correlation between the number of furnace campaigns and the resulting campaign lifetime. They calculated the median historical lifetime to be 17 years, and that the technical lifetime has increased in recent decades. Thus, the assumed lifetime is set to 20 years for retrofit in blast furnaces. Newly installed DRI plants have an estimated lifetime of 20-30 years and an average lifetime of 25 years is assumed in this study [43].

HVC (Steam cracker):

Steam crackers in many cases are very old plants that have undergone a variety of incremental investments and improvements with regard to higher efficiency, process integration, capacity increases and others. For this reason, it is difficult to assign them a lifetime. The figures in the literature range from an analysis period of 20 years [74] and lifetimes up to 30 [95] and 70 [96] years, depending on individual properties, degree of modernisation and number and type of incremental investments. However, the depreciation period and amortisation are often estimated as even shorter with 20 years in most cases [48]. In this study, an investment decision is assumed for each modernisation cycle of 25 years.

Ammonia (Steam reforming):

Ammonia production plants basically consist of two process steps: synthesis gas generation and a Haber-Bosch reactor to synthesize ammonia. The limitation to the technical lifetime results from the unit generating the synthesis gas as a Haber-Bosch reactor is stated to have long operating lifetimes of 40 [97] up to 50 [98] or even 60 [42] has an of 40-60 years, which can be prolonged by additional incremental investments. Steam methane reformers are most commonly used to supply the synthesis gas and have an economic and technical lifetime of 20 [99] to 30 [100] years. As the CO₂ emissions result from conventional synthesis gas generation, ammonia production can be decarbonised by substitution with green hydrogen and an air separation unit for nitrogen extraction. For these reasons, the assumed average lifetime of 25 years is set for reinvestment decisions on ammonia plants [101].

Methanol (Steam reforming):

Similar to ammonia, methanol production can also be separated into two process steps. First, synthesis gas generation to supply hydrogen and a carbon source, and second, the synthesis unit to produce methanol. A choice has to be made between process alternatives regarding the provision of the synthesis gas, as several alternatives are available. Conventional steam methane reformers or partial oxidation units for crude oil or coal compete with the external supply of hydrogen and CO₂ from biomass or other renewable sources. The assumed technical and economic lifetime is based on the literature and set to 25 years [102].

Appendix F: Development of hydrogen, natural gas, naphtha and coal demand

Hydrogen demand:

Appendix F1: Spatial development of hydrogen demand per product over time for low hydrogen and high CO₂ price sensitivity

Natural gas demand:

Appendix F2: Spatial development of natural gas demand per product over time for low hydrogen and high CO₂ price sensitivity

Naphtha demand:

Appendix F3: Spatial development of naphtha demand per product over time for low hydrogen and high CO₂ price sensitivity

Coal demand:

Appendix F4: Spatial development of coal demand per product over time for low hydrogen and high CO₂ price sensitivity

Supplementary material/supporting information

We provide extensive Excel files containing the result tables of the figures presented in this paper and additional very detailed information at country level. Further data or insights into the model will be made available on request.

S1: Model input data and assumptions

S1.1: The excel file transparently shows the techno-economic model inputs

S1.2: Total list of modelled industry sites with their properties

S2: Further detailed model results

S2.1: Final energy demand at country level for sensitivity 16 (4.400)

S2.2: Specific costs and their components per process for Germany for sensitivity 16 (4.400)

S2.3: Yearly total costs and their components for steel production and for all 16 sensitivities

S2.4: Yearly total costs and their components for ammonia production and for all 16 sensitivities

S2.5: Yearly total costs and their components for HVC production and for all 16 sensitivities

S2.6: Yearly total costs and their components for methanol production and for all 16 sensitivities

S2.7: Yearly total hydrogen demand and its components for all 16 sensitivities

S2.8: Cumulative investments and their components for all 16 sensitivities

S2.9: Yearly total emissions and their components for all 16 sensitivities

For some of the variables we had to focus on single countries or sensitivities for the supplementary material provided in this paper. Not all derived data can be made available due to the large quantity involved (more than 2000 Excel sheets). However, data for other sensitivities (in the case of S2.1) or other countries (in the case of S2.2) will be made available on request.

Appendix G. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2024.119117>.

References

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